

The efficiency of revolving scanning as compared to "the best possible scheme"

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The scheme for scanning the sky in option A should be chosen to maximise the total weight of the derived astrometric unknowns with certain restrictions imposed on some of the parameters, e.g. $\zeta < 45^\circ$ and $\omega < 0.5^\circ/\text{orbit}$ (ζ = angle from the Sun to the rotation axis, ω = rate of change of the direction of the axis).

Removing all such restrictions we intuitively realize that the "best" scanning scheme is that for which the pole of each great circle scan is chosen independently and at random (equal probability for every square degree of the sky). For such a "random scanning" we obtain the following expected variances of the five astrometric unknowns:

$$\begin{aligned}P_{\Delta\lambda\cos\beta} &= P_{\Delta\beta} = 2/n \\P_{\mu_\lambda\cos\beta} &= P_{\mu_\beta} = 24/nT^2 \\P_\pi &= 4/n(1 + \sin^2\beta) \\ \langle P_\pi \rangle_{\text{sky}} &= \pi/n = 3.14/n,\end{aligned}$$

where $n = T \sin(w/2)/P$ is the average number of orbits during which a specific star is observed, w is the field width and P the orbital period; T is the length of the mission.

For $T = 3$ years, $P = 95^m$, $w = 0.9^\circ$ we have $n = 130$ and the error factors

$$P_{\text{pos.}}^{1/2} = 0.124, \quad P_{\text{p.m.}}^{1/2} = 0.143 \text{ yr}^{-1}, \quad \text{and} \quad P_\pi^{1/2} = \begin{cases} 0.175 & (\beta = 0) \\ 0.143 & (\beta = 45^\circ) \\ 0.124 & (\beta = 90^\circ) \end{cases}$$

Fig. 1 in the note* not dated 77-02-12 is based on the same numbers for T , P , and w but is computed for revolving scanning with $K = 270^\circ/\zeta$. Comparison shows that revolving scanning with $\zeta = 40^\circ$ is, for most part of the sky, almost as efficient as random scanning for positions and proper motions. For parallaxes it gives however about 1.4 times larger error factors, which seems to be an unavoidable consequence of the restraint put on ζ . We conclude that revolving scanning with the proposed parameters (if technically feasible) is as efficient as any other scheme subject to similar restrictions.

* Presented at the meeting 77-02-15